

An Investigative Study on the Impact of OTT Platform on the Youth of India

Under Guidance of
Dr. Richa Tiwari (Mentor – PCL)

(Mentees):

**Shradha Murthy; Shreya Jaiswal; Paridhee Agarwal; Gudiputi Joshitha Chowdary;
Maniyatha Katariya; Srivatsa S.**

BBA Sports Management, Jain (Deemed-to-be University), Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

Abstract:

This is a research paper studying the proliferation of over OTT platforms and how it has fundamentally transformed the landscape of media consumption, providing unparalleled convenience and an extensive library of audio-visual content accessible without traditional cable or satellite. This phenomenon has gained momentum globally with increasing numbers of individuals, particularly young adults and students, embracing OTT services for their convenience to get a diverse list of programming, like movies and TV shows. However, alongside convenience and variety, concern have arisen regarding the potential societal impacts of OTT platform, particularly concerning the portrayal of uncensored content and its influence on the attitude and behavior of youth. This research paper seeks to delve into the multifaceted effects of OTT platform, specifically focusing on their impact on the young demographic in India. The study aims to address several research questions, including the perception of undergraduates towards OTT platform, the adoption and usage pattern of these platforms among Indian and the implication of OTT Content consumption on student's mental health and socialization. Employing a quantitative research design, data will be conducted through structured survey and questionnaire distributed among a sample students. The research methodology will involve both primary and secondary data sources, with statistical tools such as Correlation analysis, and we used the descriptive statistic method Ethical consideration, including informed consent and confidentiality measures, will be rigorously upheld throughout the research purpose. The scope of the study extends beyond mere quantitative analysis aiming to provide a comprehensive sociological analysis of the implication of OTT platform usage among the youth in India. By examining consumers preferences, trends and attitude towards OTT adoption, the study seeks to shed light on the broader socio-culture ramifications of the growing prominence of OTT platform in Indian media landscape.

Keywords:

OTT, Over-the-top, mental health, students , entertainment

Introduction:

"Over-the-top," is the process of accessing and production of video and audio content without the need of a cable or a satellite subscription. Over the top is popularity in the recent years because many people are realizing the advantages of OTT. The main advantage is the convenience that streaming services offer its users. A wide range of movies is available in the palm of your hand. OTT platforms offer a wide range of TV shows, movies, and original programs, allowing viewers to find something that suits their interests. Many of these services also offer live streaming options for events such as sports, news, and concerts, providing even more options and more entertainment for viewers.

The main features of OTT platforms is the ability to access content on demand, meaning that viewers can watch shows and movies at anytime and anywhere, rather than being constrained by a traditional television schedule and location. All devices like smartphones, tablets, and TV's can be used to view programs on OTT platforms.

The introduction of the OTT platform has made a wide variety of programs in various genres, languages and production styles freely available for the whole world to view. It has been increasingly used since the pandemic which started at beginning of 2020. Shows like money heist, Mirzapur, November story etc. have been continuous entertainment that can be watched nonstop at any given time of the day. The quality of contents of this show doesn't necessarily match with their life styles because the contrasting projection aspects like violence, which is affecting the lives of students which are predominantly biggest consumer in the industry. It also effects analytical thinking that humans conceptualize and its capabilities natura has enabled mankind with evolutionary processes. One article discovered that among 300+ respondents around 19 years binge- watching was associated with sadness and loneliness. Studies show that binge- watching content on such platforms has changed students' behavior in a number of ways. A number of research studies have suggested that students' mental health may suffer as a result of their excessive use of OTT platform. For example an article discovered negative platform usage among Turkish University students was connected with anxiety. Findings were also obtained where it was found that a teenager who spend who uses OTT platforms excessively has greater levels of anxiety and despair. Several research studies have shown that the effects on student's socialization and interpersonal interaction has been researched on by many studies . Another study found that teens who uses OTT platforms frequently had worse face to face communication skills and were less likely to engage in prosocial behavior the other hand, a Lee and Kim (2018) study discovered that South Korean teen use OTT platform might be a way for them to increase their social capital. Nowadays, young or students prefer using the internet. Because young people are viewed media junkies, OTT platform are swiftly starting to run and gain popularity in world.

Entertainment is seeing changes in both form and structure every decades. Despite the widespread use of OTT service, which has fundamentally altered the entertainment industry, academic have only just started to pay attention to this problems. Amazon prime hotstar Disney, Netflix, voot Zee 5, and Sony live are some of OTT platform providers in India . Now a days one of the most recent trends in entertainment and the film industry is development of Over- The-Top media platforms, which allow users to stream audio content online. Cinema and television content are governed by Central board of film certification(CBFC) and board casting programming complaint council(BCCC) although OTT service are not subject to any regulation of oversight. As a result, OTT platform are free to stream any kind of information , however it has been noted that high portion of contents that they distribute are offensive to society as whole. In recent times it observed that there are many cases, where a number of complaints have been filed against some web series

which hurting religious feelings, the content of which is immoral, obscene, and defamatory. Thus, to tighter the regime of OTT platform it is very necessary to form certain bodies, authority that watch and control the working of OTT platform.

Theatre has a large scale experience with one of the best audio and visuals. Lately with all the digital features, it provides impressive features which gives a comfortable atmosphere to watch movies. It is s the phenomenon of OTT platforms. Allocation Act adds two subsections 22A and 22B. Category 22A includes movies and audio-visual programs provided by online content providers. News and current affairs on online platforms fall under the new 22B category. On February 25, 2021, the government announced the regulatory code for OTT platforms.

For content creators, distributors, and consumers alike, understanding the trends shaping the OTT landscape is crucial. The impact of OTT media on society is multifaceted, with both positive and negative consequences. While it has provided greater convenience and accessibility for consumers, it has also raised concerns about binge-watching behavior and social isolation.

Slideshows: Slideshows are a popular feature on OTT platforms, allowing users to view a series of images or promotional content.

Content Organization (Horizontal Scroll): Horizontal scroll is a popular method for displaying a wide range of content options on OTT platforms.

User Engagement Thresholds: Understanding user engagement thresholds is essential for creating a captivating OTT experience. While the specific number of clicks leading to user disinterest can vary, it is crucial to keep users engaged from the start.

Types of media

Review of Literature:

This study was to understand the intentions of students to use Ott platforms. Raj Priya, Pias Mondal and Dr. Trinley Paldon (2021) conducted this research to explore the relationship between OTT, social gratification and customer engagement. The research focuses on how OTT has disrupted the traditional media ecosystem. It also explores how traditional media platforms such as Alt.Balaji have shifted their strategy to adhere to the latest needs which are OTT platforms. This research was performed using an online survey Google form. The pilot study was performed using 330 students. It was found that respondents are influenced positively by social gratification. According to the report's findings OTT platforms have an impact on customers intention of subscription through the mediation effect. However, the study implemented the online survey or the online limitation where some respondents did not understand integrated OTT platform technology. Chan Hernxi (2020) identified that the perception of conventional TV and OTT

streaming platforms among university students in Klang valley. He studied the difference between conventional tv and OTT platforms. Chan Hernxi (2020) has used the seven components of uses and gratification approach. The research also spoke about how many students' favorite TV shows were available in different devices on applications Despite the advantages of OTT platforms the students of Klang valley preferred conventional TV. The consistent finding was that the respondents preferred TV because it was easy to use. However, Hernxi (2020) pointed out that looking at the diversity of the audience is important for a robust conclusion.

Raj and Nair (2021) how content has changed in recent years with the latest content being original shows and analyzed the behavioral changes in how the new generation views digital entertainment. They observed players like Netflix, Amazon prime and Hulu. The limitation was that this study was conducted during the lockdown period which may have led to respondents being biased in favor of OTT platforms. Chen (2019) research revealed a significant degree of resemblance and usability shared by these two modes of television consumption. The study prompted a critical inquiry into the determinants influencing viewer preferences in a highly competitive media environment.

Menon (2022) focused on OTT subscriptions and unveiled viewers' intentions not only to acquire but also to maintain subscriptions to OTT video streaming platforms. He highlighted the perceived amusement and convenience associated with navigating OTT platforms, providing crucial insights into the factors driving the transition from traditional television to OTT. Kim (2021) study delved into the OTT bundled service market. Their research explored consumer preferences for packaged offerings within the OTT domain, offering valuable insights into viewer choices and expectations in the Korean market. However, the study limits itself to understanding Korean dimer and needs deep comprehensive research on subscription behavior and market dynamics

Purdy (2028) study found that smaller competitors face challenges in establishing their presence in this competitive market, where content is paramount. However, they can attract more consumers by focusing on curated content, addressing account sharing issues, setting the right pricing strategy, and enhancing customer relations to reduce customer churn. While price is an essential factor for OTT service selection, content remains the primary driver of consumer choices. The Big 3 are valued for their diverse content libraries, with "access to a vast library of content" being the top reason users subscribe to these services. Small players who align with these factors are more likely to draw a significant subscriber base. Singh (2020) claimed that the OTT platform has experienced a surge in consumption and subscribers due to the impact of COVID-19. According to a recent survey by InMobi, 46% of viewers are now watching more online content. Experts predict further growth in OTT services as traditional television channels face content shortages caused by lockdowns. Sundaravel and Elangovan (2020) demonstrated how the growth of OTT would hurt cable TV's penetration in India. Therefore, traditional TV station should get ready for a paradigm shift brought about by OTT platform by focusing on producing high quality content that can rival the content that is available online.

Sadana and Sharma (2021), is to examine how young consumer in India are increasingly choosing over the top (OTT) platform over traditional pay TV service (cable TV/ DTH), as well as the important variables that influence such preferences and the gamification of contents. Most studies have focused on urban consumer. Research on OTT adoption in semi-urban and rural areas is limited. Not much research on supply-sides like content strategy, pricing, partnership etc. for OTT player in India Understanding the OTT TV revolution over the past ten years, increased internet usage, access to, and availability of many screens and devices have fueled the development and expansion of OTT platforms. OTT TV refers to high-definition video material that is streamed directly from the provider onto a user's screen (such as a mobile device, tablet,

laptop, TV, etc.) through Internet Protocol over a public network. The fact that OTT circumvents cable, broadcast, and satellite television platforms, the businesses that often operate as a controller or distributor of such content, and democratizes content accessibility and empowers the customer in several ways, is what is crucial to comprehend in this case. The majority of the literature 302 that is accessible addressing the development and uptake of OTTs points to this important distinction.

Livingstone (2003) Online streaming services have entered the industry to gain market share. This internet video stream is substantially different from typical television in terms of its content, features, and setting. It is still difficult to assess how traditional media theories and approaches might contribute to research on evolving audiences and their listening habits. Haridas & Deepak (2020) In their study, analyzed all online streaming services, separating out various platforms based on user preferences which tells us how different users perceive entertainment in a different manner also underlining the behavioral pattern of customers of the entertainment industry.

According to Menon (2020), restrictions imposed in the wake of the COVID-19 epidemic dramatically altered the structure of media and leisure consumption. Lockdowns prevented people from leaving for leisure or employment, therefore public activity gradually shifted to online platforms. Social networking sites on the internet gave people the opportunity to keep in touch with their family, friends, partners, neighbors, and other people. When the authorities requested that external entertainment channels (outside of the home) be shut down, the modes of home entertainment continued to flourish and evolve. According to Deloitte's "Digital Media: Rise of On- Demand Content" research from 2017, the availability of reasonably priced smartphones and improved 4G internet connectivity have increased demand for video on demand entertainment services.

Menon (2020) states that limitations forced in the wake of Covid-19 pandemic significantly changed the consumption pattern for media and entertainment too. As lockdowns kept individuals from wandering out, either for recreation or work, public activity progressively moved to online stages. It was noticed that with the rise of OTT, time spent with families, companions, partners, neighbors and others have become less. With external channels of entertainment (Out of Homebased entertainment) shut by government request, the home- based entertainment modes showed consistent growth and development. Deloitte (2017) report on "Digital Media: Rise of On-demand Content" stated that the availability of affordable smartphones and better internet 4G connectivity has given rise to the demand for video on demand entertainment services.

Mann et al., (2015) in report "Digital Video & the connected consumer" tells us that with 50% of smartphone app users who are aged between 18-24 years, media platforms are targeting the demography of a younger audience.

It was also noted that most Indians do not like to spend money to watch content online.

Objectives:

- To study the impact of uncensored content on the youth of the country.
- To study on adoption and usage of OTT platforms on Indians.
- To study the perception of undergraduates in the Indian region towards OTT Platform.
- To study into the different types of content and their market share.

- To analyze the positive or a negative impact of OTT platforms on students.

Research methodology:

This study adopts a quantitative research design to investigate the impact of Over-The-Top (OTT) platforms on students. Primary data is collected through surveys and questionnaires, focusing on OTT usage patterns and its impact. Additionally, secondary data is gathered from previous papers to provide context. The collected data will be analyzed using statistical tools like correlation analysis, mean average calculations, and descriptive statistics, to derive numerical insights and relationships, thus helping us understand OTT platform effects on students. This study's research design is primarily descriptive in nature. There is a survey including questionnaire responses from the participants. Around 150 people are included in the study's sample, which are taken into account. The survey is broken up into sections like demographics, subscription fees, convenience, and OTT consumption habit, and it includes current questions on OTT usage as well as questions about the past usage patterns and viewpoints. A questionnaire was utilized to gather data, with the question carefully crafted after thorough research on the topic. The questionnaire aims to offer the insight into the effect of OTT platform on the viewing experience. The respondents' response will be noted and an appropriate analysis is performed in light of the response.

The scope of the study lies in the fact that this study is a sociological analysis of the various ramifications of the impact of Cable TV and Online Streaming services as an important medium of mass communication. The scope of the study enables the viewers to choose the online video streaming services and also to identify the attitude towards the change in the way of delivery of mass media. It also analyzed their preferences on various genres and various streaming applications. The study finds how it affects the climate change and also gives suggestions on how to enhance energy consumption.

As part of secondary research, the researchers reviewed reports from different organizations, studied past global literature regarding OTT adoption and trends, referred white papers, newspapers and numerous other research reports. Qualitative and quantitative primary research was done to understand the thoughts and opinions of consumers regarding OTT adoption and content consumption during COVID-19.

The Complete Details of research paper are :-

Type of research:

For this study, a descriptive research methodology was used to analyze the effect of OTT platform on youth of India. The study involved collecting and analyzing data from various sources, including academic literature, industry reports, and primary sources such as interviews with professionals and surveys.

The descriptive research methodology was chosen as it allowed for a comprehensive and detailed analysis of the effect of OTT platform on youth of India. Methodology involved the collection of both numerical data and descriptive data to gain better comprehension of the How does OTT platform is gaining popularity as well as its future trends. The data was then analyzed using various tools, such as statistical analysis and content analysis, to identify key patterns and themes.

The descriptive study approach allowed us to provide a comprehensive overview of the OTT platform effects and future prospects. By utilizing a descriptive research methodology, we were able to identify key elements that has driven the OTT platform, offering valuable perspective that is beneficial for both business and policymakers.

The descriptive study methodology proved to be an effective tool for analyzing the impact of OTT platform on youth of India. The data collected and analyzed allowed us to draw meaningful

Received: 2 March 2024

Revised: 12 March 2024

Final Accepted 27 March 2024

Copyright © authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10884737>

conclusions and provide valuable perspective into the effect of OTT platform and future prospects in India.

The sampling Method used:

In order to collect data for this study, a probability sampling method was used. Probability sampling is a technique used to guarantee that every individual within the population has an equitable opportunity for selection in the sample. This approach was selected because it enabled us to acquire a sample that accurately represent the population under the study. sampling frame for this study was individuals who are basically a subscriber of OTT platform and regular user of OTT platform . A random sampling method was used to select participants for the survey. The random selection of participants ensured that each member of the population had an equal chance of being selected as part of the sample. This method helped to reduce bias and increase the reliability and validity of the study's findings.

The survey was conducted online, and participants were invited to participate via email and social media platforms. The survey consisted of a series of questions designed to gather data on the effect of OTT platform on youth of India, including factors such as usage, satisfaction levels, and preferences. The data collected was analyzed using statistical analysis techniques to identify patterns and trends.

Overall, the probability sampling method was an effective tool for collecting data for this study. The random selection of participants ensured that the sample accurately reflected the population under investigation, and the gathered data yielded valuable insights for our study. By using this method, we were able to increase the reliability and validity of the study's findings, making them more generalizable to the wider population.

The sample area:

For this study, the subset area was restricted to the city of Bangalore, India. Bangalore is one of the fastest-growing cities in India and has a enough number of youth who use OTT platform on daily basis.

To get sample of the population being studied, a probability sampling method was used. The sampling frame for this study was individuals who use OTT platform as a source of their entertainment . A random sampling method was used to select participants for the survey, which was conducted online.

The sample size for this study was established through statistical computation, considering both the population size and the desired degree of precision. A sample size of 160 participants was chosen to ensure that the study possessed adequate statistical power to identify significant disparities and correlation among various. The analysis of the data provided insights into our study including factors such as usage patterns, satisfaction levels, and preferences.

Overall, by focusing on the city of Bangalore as the sample area, we were able to obtain a detailed understanding of how OTT platform has effecting the youth. The results of this study can be used to find whether OTT platform has positive or negative effect on youth.

The Survey method and through the medium:

To collect information for this research paper, a questionnaire was developed and administered through Google Forms . Google forms is an internet based survey platform enabling the design of tailored questionnaire and the gathering of responses digitally. The questionnaire was designed to gather information on the effect of OTT on the youth, including factors such as usage patterns, satisfaction levels, and preferences.

The questionnaire was distributed via email and social media platforms to individuals or students who use OTT platform on daily basis . Participants were informed of the study's purpose and assured of the confidentiality of their responses.

The use of Google Forms for this study provided several benefits. First, it allowed for the rapid collection of a large amount of data from a diverse pool of participants. Second, it facilitated the analysis of the data through automatic data storage and organization, making it easier to perform statistical analysis.

Overall, the use of Google Forms for this study was an effective way to gather information on our study . The questionnaire was well-designed to collect the necessary information, and the use of Google Forms facilitated the collection and analysis of the data.

Data interpretation and analysis :

Out of 118 people in the group, there are 62 females and 56 males. Nobody in the group identified as a third gender or chose not to say. This tells us that the group is mostly made up of males and females, but there might be other genders not represented here.

Out of the total, 76 individuals fall within the income range of 0-500,000. There are 17 people with incomes ranging from 500,001 to 750,000, and 16 individuals earning between 750,001 and 1,000,000. Additionally, 6 individuals earn between 1,000,001 and 1,250,000, while 4 individuals have incomes exceeding 1,250,000.

Among the group, 68 individuals are aged between 18 and 25 years old. There are 24 individuals falling within the age range of 24 to 30, and 16 individuals aged between 30 and 36. Notably, there are no individuals in the age groups of 37-45 or 46 and above.

Within the dataset, 10 individuals have completed their education at the Higher Secondary level, while 8 individuals have achieved a Senior Secondary education. The majority, 68 individuals, have completed an Undergraduate degree, followed by 30 individuals who hold a Postgraduate qualification. Only 2 individuals have obtained a Professional or Doctoral Degree.

Among the surveyed individuals, 70 identify as students, while 6 are homemakers. In terms of employment, 23 work in the Private Sector, while 7 are employed in the Public Sector. Additionally, 13 individuals are self-employed, professionals, or business owners.

qs	9. preference of media channel	11. Impact on procrastination time	12. preference of content	14. advantage on the youth	15. individual choice and its impact .	25. Impact on academic and professional	28. Impact on mental health	30. OTT platforms and guidance
----	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	---------------------------	----------------------------	--	---	-----------------------------	--------------------------------

						capabili ties		
Mean	3.491	3.550	3.686	3.491	3.491	3.491	3.491	3.491
Stand ard Error	0.122	0.122	0.115	0.122	0.122	0.122	0.122	0.122

9. preference of OTT platforms	11. Impact on procrastination time .	12. preference of content	14. Advantage of OTT platforms	15. individual choice and its impact
1.000				
-0.130				
0.950	1.000			
0.837	0.874	1.000		
0.128	0.174	0.172		
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	1.000
0.310	0.366	0.242	0.310	0.310
0.162	0.219	0.165	0.162	0.162
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	1.000
0.199	0.238	0.182	0.199	0.199
0.219	0.205	0.172	0.219	0.219
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	1.000
0.098	0.089	0.016	0.098	0.098
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	1.000
0.125	0.087	0.032	0.125	0.125
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	1.000
0.071	0.034	0.077	0.071	0.071
0.044	0.017	0.005	0.044	0.044
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	1.000
0.211	0.179	0.228	0.211	0.211
1.000	0.950	0.837	1.000	1.000

As per the recent survey conducted youngsters are indeed satisfied with the advantage of OTT platform, and they actively participate in survey to voice their opinion. They appreciate the wide variety of contents available, which allows them to explore their interest and discovered new movies and shows. The convenience of being able to watch their favorite content anytime, anywhere is another aspect that resonates with them.

According to the findings of the survey, people’s opinions about the effect of OTT platforms vary based on the type of content they consume. The diverse range of content available on OTT platforms means that individuals’ perceptions of whether the platforms have a positive or negative effect depend on the specific shows or movies they watch. Per the survey result, a significant consensus exist among participates regarding the influence of OTT platform on the academic and profession aptitude of youth post covid 19 outbreak. Many respondents share the view that heightened involvement with OTT platform has had an adverse effect on their capabilities.

Received: 2 March 2024

Revised: 12 March 2024

Final Accepted 27 March 2024

Copyright © authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10884737>

According to the survey, there is widespread agreement among respondents that they have experienced numerous adverse effects on their mental health as a result of the content available on the OTT platform.

As participants engage in the survey, they express a neutral agreement with the statement that OTT platform have the potential to offer beneficial educational content, provided that youngster is guided appropriately with suitable guidelines and awareness building efforts. This suggests that while there is recognition of the educational potential of these platforms, there is also an acknowledgement of the needs for proactive measures to ensure the youth navigate the content responsibility and effective. In the survey, Students agree with statement , and acknowledge that their time spent on the OTT platform has led to increase procrastination in other essential aspect of daily lives. They admit that the allure of streaming services often leads them to prioritize entertainment over academic or personal responsibilities, resulting in delay and distractions. This recognition of the impact of OTT platform on their procrastination habits suggest a level of self awareness among the students regarding their media consumption habits. Despite this acknowledgement, however, there seems to be sense of contentment with the enjoyment derived from streaming contents , even if it comes at the expense of productivity.

As a participants engage in the survey, they express satisfaction with the abundance of the content available on OTT platform, indicating a preference for diverse range of option. Many participants appreciate the convenience of having access to a vast Library of content at their fingertips, allowing them to discover new shows and movies and documentaries that align with their tastes.

In the survey, the participants express satisfaction with the statement indicating their general preference for watching content on OTT platform. They highlight the convenience and flexibility offered by these platforms, allowing them to access a wide range of content from the from the comfort of their own home. Many participants appreciate the ability to choose from diverse selection of shows, movies, documentaries, tailored to their specific interest and preferences

Findings and discussions:

Positive correlation

Correlation of the preference of watching OTT content with procrastination time-

Many people, prefer watching content on OTT platforms such as Netflix or Hulu., for students, spending time on these platforms can increase procrastination, taking away from other important activities. However, the abundance of content on OTT platforms makes them more appealing. So, there's a positive correlation between preferring content on OTT platforms and spending more time procrastinating ,as well as having a preference for the content available on these platforms .

Correlation between the impact of OTT platform with procrastination time and the impact of covid-19-

The correlation between the impact of OTT platforms on students' procrastination time and their beliefs about the advantages of OTT platforms for youngsters can be seen positively. When students spend more time on OTT platforms, it can initially increase procrastination. However, this increased exposure to OTT platforms also gives them access to educational content, documentaries, and informative series, individuals perceive the impact of OTT platforms as positive or negative based on the content they choose to engage with, indicating a correlation between the types of content available and users' perceptions. Increased exposure to diverse content on OTT platforms can lead to varied perceptions and understandings of their benefits. The content available on smaller or regional platforms, suggesting that individuals find value in diverse content offerings beyond mainstream platforms, reinforcing the positive correlation between OTT engagement and perceptions of its advantages. The paper highlights concerns about the impact of OTT engagement

on academic and professional capabilities post-COVID-19, indicating a recognition of the significant role these platforms play in youths' lives, further supporting the positive correlation between OTT engagement and its perceived benefits. Referring to the paper about covid 19 and OTT platforms by G Gupta(2019) was useful.

correlation between the availability of content and their influence on users-
The increase in preferred content on OTT platforms positively correlates with satisfaction levels regarding smaller and regional platforms. As individuals find more content they enjoy on OTT platforms, they may also discover and appreciate the offerings of smaller platforms, leading to increased satisfaction overall. The tendency to binge-watch new age TV shows like K-Drama on OTT platforms isn't great and can contribute to this positive correlation. As people explore diverse content options on OTT platforms, they may develop preference for different types of content, including those offered by smaller or regional platforms. This gives production houses a chance to create more diverse content .The engagement with OTT platforms post-COVID-19 may also positively influence content preferences. As individuals spend more time on OTT platforms, they have greater exposure to a variety of content, leading to a deeper understanding of their preferences and a higher likelihood of finding content they enjoy. This increased engagement may lead to greater satisfaction with both OTT and smaller/regional platforms, reinforcing the positive correlation between content preferences and satisfaction levels.

However

Correlation between prefer to watch contents on OTT platform with increased procrastination time for other activities of routine life

The increased in preferred to watch content on OTT platform negativity correlates with procrastination for other significant activities of daily routine. As Increases screen time on OTT platform can leads to procrastination, where students delay important task in favor of binge watching shows and movies. This can negativity impact daily routine by taking away time from essential activities such as studying, exercising or socializing. Additionally, Prolonged Screen time can affect sleep quality and mental health, leading to decreased productivity and overall well being. When students spend more time on OTT platform, they often find themselves engrossed in watching Contents for extended period, which can leads to procrastination, As a result of procrastination students may find themselves failing behind in their academic responsibility, leading to increased stress, anxiety and lower academic performance.

Correlation of adverse effects on mental health due to OTT platform with missing out deadlines for important activities

The correlation between trend to miss out deadlines for most important activities of daily routine due to diverged OTT distraction and age appropriate Contents rationing on OTT has been seen negative. As people get more and more attracted with the contents available on OTT platform which leads to miss out deadlines. The prevalence of OTT platform has introduced a new challenges in managing daily routines, as many individuals find themselves Ignoring age appropriate Contents recommendation may expose individuals to Contents that is unsuitable for age or maturity level, leading to potential psychological or emotional harm as well as consume large chunk of time leaving insufficient room for completing important activities. Moreover, the abundance of options on these platforms can leads to difficulties in periodizing task over entertainment, fostering a tendency to procrastinate Switching focus from consuming OTT platform content completing task becomes increasingly challenging, further exacerbating the problem. Additionally, for some OTT platform serves as a means of escapism from stress or responsibility, perpetuating the cycle of distraction and delaying the completion of crucial tasks. Age-appropriate Contents rationing on OTT platform is

crucial for ensuring that viewer, especially children are exposed to suitable material. However, not considering these rating or guidelines when selecting what to watch can have negative impact. Content on over-the-top platform can negatively affect mental health due to excessive exposure to violence, explicit content, unrealistic body standards and addictive binge-watching behaviour, this can lead to Increase stress, anxiety, depression, and poor sleep Patterns among view. Correlation between prefer to watch movie on Traditional theatre and satisfied with content available on smaller platform

Negative impact of OTT platform over traditional TV. Both OTT platform and traditional TV can contribute to excessive screen time, leading to potential health issues such as eye strain, disrupted sleep patterns and sedentary behaviour. However OTT platform may pose higher risk due to on demand nature of Content allowing user to binge watching for extended periods without breaks. OTT platform offers a wider range of contents, including user generated content and niche programming, which may not always adhere to strict content guidelines, Traditional TV is subject to regulatory standards and may have stricter content control in place, particularly during certain time of day when children are more likely to be watch.

Limitations & Conclusion:

While the study provides valuable insights into the correlations between OTT platform usage, procrastination, content preferences, and their impacts, there are several limitations to consider:

The study's findings are limited by the demographics of the surveyed population. The sample size might not be representative of the broader population, potentially skewing the results. For instance, the study lacks representation from individuals who do not engage with OTT platforms, which could lead to biases in the reported correlations. The data collected relies on self-reported information, which can be subject to biases such as social desirability bias or memory recall issues. Participants may not accurately report their behaviors or experiences with OTT platforms, leading to potential inaccuracies in the reported correlations.

Causality vs. Correlation: The study focuses on identifying correlations between variables but does not establish causality. While correlations provide valuable insights, they do not necessarily imply causation. Without experimental designs or longitudinal studies, it's challenging to determine the directionality of the relationships observed in the data. The study primarily focuses on correlations related to OTT platform usage, procrastination, and content preferences. It may overlook other relevant factors that could influence these relationships, such as individual personality traits, socio-economic status, or cultural differences.

The study's findings may not be generalizable across different cultural or socio-economic contexts. Cultural attitudes towards OTT platforms, procrastination, and content consumption can vary widely, impacting the observed correlations. Thus, caution should be exercised when applying the study's findings to diverse populations. The study's findings may be influenced by temporal factors such as technological advancements, shifts in content consumption trends, or changes in socio-political landscapes. As such, the correlations identified in the study may not remain stable over time.

While the study acknowledges the potential negative impacts of OTT platform usage on mental health, it may not provide a comprehensive understanding of these effects. Factors such as individual coping mechanisms, social support networks, or pre-existing mental health conditions are not adequately addressed. The study's recommendations for addressing the identified correlations may lack specificity or feasibility. Implementing effective interventions to mitigate the negative impacts of OTT platform usage requires careful consideration of multiple factors beyond the scope of the study.

In conclusion, the study provides valuable insights into the complex interplay between OTT platform usage, procrastination behaviors, content preferences, and their impacts on individuals' daily lives. Through the analysis of correlations, several key findings have emerged, shedding light on both positive and negative associations within this context.

On the positive side, the study highlights the strong correlation between the preference for OTT content consumption and increased procrastination time. This correlation underscores the allure of OTT platforms like Netflix or Hulu, particularly among students, as they offer a wide array of content choices. Additionally, the study reveals a positive correlation between OTT platform engagement and perceptions of its benefits, especially in providing educational and informative content, particularly relevant during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Moreover, the study suggests a positive correlation between the availability of diverse content on OTT platforms and user satisfaction, including smaller and regional platforms. This finding underscores the importance of content diversity in catering to varied preferences and interests, potentially leading to greater satisfaction among users.

However, the study also uncovers negative correlations, particularly concerning the adverse effects of OTT platform usage on individuals' daily routines and mental health. Increased screen time on OTT platforms is associated with heightened procrastination, leading to neglect of essential activities such as studying, exercising, or socializing. Furthermore, the study identifies a negative correlation between OTT distractions and meeting deadlines for important tasks, highlighting the detrimental impact of excessive OTT consumption on time management and productivity.

Moreover, the research highlights the adverse effects of OTT platform on conventional Television watching behavior, mentioning potential health hazards linked to extended screen exposure and the anytime accessibility of OTT content consumption. In light of these findings, several implications emerge for both individuals and policymakers. Individuals should be mindful of their OTT consumption habits and strive for a balanced approach to screen time to mitigate the negative impacts on productivity, mental health, and overall well-being. Policymakers may consider implementing measures to promote responsible OTT usage, including age-appropriate content ratings and guidelines to safeguard viewers, especially children, from potentially harmful content.

Overall, while OTT platforms offer unprecedented access to diverse content and entertainment options, it is crucial to recognize and address the associated challenges to ensure a healthy and balanced media consumption landscape. Further research is warranted to delve deeper into these correlations and explore potential interventions to mitigate the negative impacts of excessive OTT platform usage.

Future Scope:

The provided correlation data offers valuable insights into individuals' attitudes and behaviors regarding Over-The-Top (OTT) platforms, particularly in comparison to traditional entertainment mediums like theaters and television channels. Let's delve into a comprehensive summary of these correlations.

OTT platforms have become increasingly popular among individuals, with a strong preference indicated for consuming content through these digital channels. This preference seems to be especially prominent among students, who admit that their engagement with OTT platforms has led to increased procrastination, impacting their routine activities. However, the allure of OTT content

is evident, as individuals express a liking for the variety and abundance of content available on these platforms.

While the convenience and vast content library of OTT platforms are appreciated, concerns regarding increased screen time and its effect on downtime are acknowledged to a lesser extent. Despite these concerns, there's a widespread belief in the advantages of OTT platforms, particularly for youngsters, who benefit from the diverse content offerings catering to various interests and preferences.

The impact of OTT platforms on individuals' viewing habits is notable, with a significant inclination towards consuming movies and TV shows on these platforms rather than through traditional mediums like theaters or television channels. The rise of binge-watching culture, particularly for new-age content such as K-Drama, underscores the immersive nature of OTT platforms in individuals' lives.

As the OTT landscape continues to evolve, individuals express willingness to explore smaller, lesser-known platforms beyond the dominant players. Satisfaction with the content available on these smaller or regional platforms is relatively high, suggesting a demand for niche and localized content offerings.

However, concerns surrounding account sharing on OTT platforms and potential adverse effects on mental health due to certain content types are also acknowledged. Nevertheless, individuals exhibit a degree of awareness regarding age-appropriate content ratings, indicating a consideration for content suitability when making viewing choices.

Moreover, there's a recognition of the educational potential of OTT platforms, provided that appropriate guidelines and awareness initiatives are in place to guide youth towards beneficial content consumption. The recent merger of traditional theater chains like PVR and INOX is perceived as a strategic move to compete with the growing dominance of OTT platforms, reflecting the shifting dynamics within the entertainment industry.

Overall, the correlation data highlights a complex interplay of preferences, concerns, and beliefs surrounding OTT platforms. While there's a strong affinity for the convenience and variety offered by these platforms, individuals also acknowledge the need for balance and responsible consumption, particularly among younger demographics.

Enhanced Regulation and Standards: This includes robust content ratings, age-appropriate recommendations, and stringent enforcement mechanisms to protect children from harmful content.

Promotion of Educational Content: OTT platforms should invest in the creation and promotion of high-quality educational content that aligns with educational objectives and standards. Collaborations with educational institutions, experts, and content creators can ensure the accuracy, relevance, and effectiveness of educational programs.

Responsible Advertising Practices: OTT platforms should adopt transparent and ethical advertising practices, especially concerning children's content. Clear labeling of sponsored content, age-appropriate advertising standards, and limitations on targeted advertising to children can help mitigate the impact of commercial influences on children's behavior and preferences.

In conclusion, while OTT platforms offer significant opportunities for children's entertainment and education during the COVID-19 pandemic, they also pose various limitations and challenges. By addressing regulatory gaps, enhancing parental controls, promoting educational content, bridging the digital divide, and adopting responsible advertising practices, stakeholders can maximize the benefits of OTT platforms while safeguarding children's well-being and development in the digital age.

Reference:

Chen, Y.-N. K. (2019). Competitions between OTT TV platforms and traditional television in Taiwan: A niche analysis. *Telecommunications Policy*, 43(9), 101793. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2018.10.006>

Gomathi, S., & Christy, V. (2021). Viewer's Perception Towards 'OTT' Platform During Pandemic (with special reference to Coimbatore city). *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 9(8), 593-693.

Gupta, G., & Singharia, K. (2021). Consumption of OTT media streaming in COVID-19 lockdown: Insights from PLS analysis. *Vision*, 25(1), 36-46.

Hemalatha, T. M., Kumar, K., & Kumar, S. (2022). A Study on Customer Satisfaction on OTT Platforms during Covid19 Pandemic Period. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 10, 1742-1745.

Kim, S., Lee, C., Lee, J., & Kim, J. (2021). Over-the-top bundled services in the Korean broadcasting and telecommunications market: Consumer preference analysis using a mixed logit model. *Telematics and Informatics*, 61, 101599.

Kim, T. Y., & Shin, D. H. (2017). The survival strategy of branded content in the over-the-top (OTT) environment: Eye-tracking and Q-methodology approach in digital product placement. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(7), 1081-1092.

Maleswar, S., & Bajaj, S. (2020). Acceptance of OTT Video Streaming Platforms in India During COVID-19: Extending UTAUT2 with Content Availability. *Journal of Content, Community & Communication*, 12(6), 89-106.

Menon, D. (2022). Purchase and continuation intentions of over-the-top (OTT) video streaming platform subscriptions: a uses and gratification theory perspective. *Telematics and Informatics Reports*, 5, 100006.

Negi, V., & Gupta, S. (2020). A Systematic Review of Literature on the Changing Consumption Patterns of Youth through OTT Platforms during the Covid-19 Lockdown. *Journal of Optoelectronics Laser*, 41(4), 693-704.

Priya, R., Mondal, D. P., & Paldon, T. (2021). Understanding the intentions of students to use OTT platforms. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology*, 8(1), 671- 677.

Puthiyakath, H. H., & Goswami, M. P. (2021). Is Over the Top Video Platform the Game Changer over Traditional TV Channels in India? A Niche Analysis. *Asia Pacific Media Educator*, 31, 133-150.

Shin, D., Lim, J. S., Ahmad, N., & Ibahrine, M. (2022). Understanding user sensemaking in fairness and transparency in algorithms: algorithmic sensemaking in over-the-top platform. *AI & SOCIETY*, 1-14.

Sundaravel, E., & Elangovan, N. (2020). Emergence and future of Over-the-top (OTT) video services in India: an analytical research. *International Journal of Business, Management and Social Research*, 8(2), 489-499.

Tan, C. S. (2021). Gamifying OTT: a study on consumer attitudes toward game elements and OTT media service provider brands in gamification. *Young Consumers*, 22(3), 328- 347.

Camerillieri, A., M & Falzon, L. (2020). Understanding motivations to use online streaming services: integrating the technology acceptance model (TAM) and the uses and gratifications theory (UGT). *Spanish Journal of Marketing-Ahead-of-print*.

Cebeci, Ince & Turkcan. (2019). Understanding the Intention to Use Netflix: An Extended Technology Acceptance Model Approach. *International Review of Management and Marketing*. Vol. 9(6), p. 152-157. [4]

Charness, N., & Boot, W.R. (2009). Aging and Information Technology Use. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*. Vol. 18(5), p. 253-258.

Danping, Lee, Lau, & Yang. (2018). Strategic response to Industry 4.0: an empirical investigation on the Chinese automotive industry. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*. Vol. 118(3), p. 589-605.

Dasgupta & Grover. (2019). Understanding adoption factors of over-the-top video services among millennial consumers. *International Journal of Computer Engineering & Technology*. Vol. 10(1),p.61-71

Ahuja, R. (2020). A Study of Effects of Web Series & Streaming Content on Indian Youth. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 8(9), 1042-1056.

Choudhary, R. L., Bhimawat, S. B., & Jain, K. H. (2016). Effect of internet utilization on overall performance of agricultural research scholars of MPUAT, Rajasthan. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 52(2), 188-191.

Dasgupta, S., & Grover, P. (2019). Understanding adoption factors of over-the-top video services among millennial consumers. *International Journal of Computer Engineering & Technology*, 10(1), 61-71.

Emmanuel, A. P., Ibrahim, M., & Ogurinde, O. (2019). Effects of social media on the Academic Performances of Students of Faculty of Agriculture, Kogi State University, Anyigba Nigeria. *Journal of Extension Education*, 30(4).

Ghalawat, S., Yadav, E., Kumar, M., Kumari, N., Goyal, M., Girdhar, A., & Agarwal, S. (2021). Factors Influencing Consumers Choice of Streaming Over the top (OTT) Platforms. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 57(3), 99–101.

Goswami, M. P., Padhi, S. R., Bakshi, S., & Puthiyakath, H. H. (2020). Susceptibility of social media users to fake news: A study among Indian youth in the light of COVID-19. *Humanities and Social Science Studies*, 9(2), 1–15.

Jose, R. (2020). Factors influencing the shift from traditional TV to OTT platforms in India. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(7), 4044-4051.

Kumari, T. (2020). A Study on Growth of Over the Top (OTT) Video Services in India. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 9(3), 68-73.

Mishra, A., Singh, J., Maurya, A. S., & Malik, J. S. (2022). Effect of socio-personal traits of farmers on their perception towards social media. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 57(4), 71-74.

Kim, J., Kim, S., & Nam, C. (2016). Competitive dynamics in the Korean video platform market: Traditional pay TV platforms vs. OTT platforms. *Telematics and Informatics*, 33(2), 711-721.

Patnaik, R., Shah, R., & More, U. (2021). Rise of OTT platforms: effect of the C-19 pandemic. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 18(7), 2277-2287.

Sadana, M., & Sharma, D. (2021). How over-the-top (OTT) platforms engage young consumers over traditional pay television service? An analysis of changing consumer preferences and gamification. *Young Consumers*, 22(3), 348-367.

Saranya, M. B., & Ravichandran, K. A STUDY ON CONSUMERS CHOICE IN OTT AND THE IMPACT OF ITS STREAMING CONTENT AMONG YOUTH IN CHENNAI
Rahul, M., & DineshBabu, S. (2021).

A comparative study on ott platform censorship and policies in india. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 25(6), 11160-11167.

Samriti, D., & Sharma, P. (2020). OTT-existing censorship laws and recommendations. Available at SSRN 3735027.

Manoj, A., & Asif, E. (2021). Content Regulation and Censorship: OTT Platforms.

GN, P. (2023). An Analysis on the Censorship and the OTT Platforms. Available at SSRN 4468339.

Kanojia, S. (2023). Creative freedom and censorship: A comparative analysis of regulatory framework for OTT contents in the UK, India, and China. *Journal of Liberty and International Affairs*, 9(3), 265-280.

+Kanojia, S. (2023). Creative freedom and censorship: A comparative analysis of regulatory framework for OTT contents in the UK, India, and China. *Journal of Liberty and International Affairs*, 9(3), 265-280.

Agrawal, A., & Shankar, R. (2020). No Objections: Constitutional Analysis of Censorship & Film Certification on OTT Platforms. Available at SSRN 3768466.

Bajwa, S. S. (2023). Popularity of ott platforms in India: An analytical study. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 13(8), 38-50.

Patnaik, R., Shah, R., & More, U. (2021). Rise of OTT platforms: effect of the C-19 pandemic. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 18(7), 2277-2287.

Parikh, N. (2020). The emergence of OTT platforms during the pandemic and its future scope. Pandey, S., Choi, M., & Park, S. (2019). The evolution of over the top (OTT): Standardization, key players and challenges. *Majlesi Journal of Electrical Engineering*, 13(4), 81-87.

Sundaravel, E., & Elangovan, N. (2020). Emergence and future of Over-the-top (OTT) video services in India: An analytical research. *International Journal of Business, Management and Social Research*, 8(2), 489-499.

Isa, A. M., Mahmud, W. A. W., Sulaiman, W. I. W., Pitchan, M. A., & Mamat, S. (2020). OTT Media and Content Regulation: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Test Engineering and Management*, 82, 9655-9665.

Manoj, A., & Asif, E. (2021). Content Regulation and Censorship: OTT Platforms. Singla, H. (2020). Self-Regulation by Over-the-Top Platforms: A Study in Context of Video Streaming Services in India. *Issue 4 Int'l JL Mgmt. & Human.*, 3, 1626.

Wadhvani, M. (2021). Ott Streaming—A Conceptual Frame Work And Regulatory Approach. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 12(11), 5977-5982.

Chawla, M. G., & Buch, N. (2023). Regulation Of Web-Based Entertainment In India: Evaluating Self-Regulation Over Censorship As A Mechanism For Regulating Ott Platforms. *Journal of Namibian Studies: History Politics Culture*, 36, 134-155.

Kudeshia, A., & Jain, S. (2022). Regulation of OTT Platforms: Need for a Separate Legislation. *Issue 6 Int'l JL Mgmt. & Human.*, 5, 1848.

Ranjan, A. (2022). Regulation of OTT Platform: Is There a Need for Censorship?. *Issue 2 Indian JL & Legal Rsch.*, 4, 1.

Rahul, M., & DineshBabu, S. (2021). A comparative study on ott platform censorship and policies in india. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 25(6), 11160-11167.

Kumar, M. K., & Gangwar, R. (2022). Necessity of OTT Regulation in Indian Context. *Bayan College International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(2), 78-90.

Bhattacharyya, S. S., Goswami, S., Mehta, R., & Nayak, B. (2022). Examining the factors influencing adoption of over the top (OTT) services among Indian consumers. *Journal of Science and Technology Policy Management*, 13(3), 652-682.